

Research Article

Selected anthropometric measurements association with performance of ball badminton players

B. Gowri Naidu¹, C. S. R. Naveen Kumar²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Education, Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies, Etcherla, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh, India, ²Assistant Director of Physical Education, Rajiv Gandhi University of Knowledge Technologies, Nuzvid, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was relationship among anthropometric measurements and ball badminton player's performance. The 82 male ball badminton players were selected from national level representation in Andhra Pradesh on non-randomly by purposive sample which was used. Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation was used to analysis of the collected data on anthropometric measurements are height (0.585*), sitting height (0.259*), weight (0.364*), palm span (0.239*), upper arm length (0.462*), forearm length (0.299*), hand length (0.379*), upper leg length (0.627*), lower leg length (0.389*), chest circumference (0.397*), wrist circumference (0.473*), thigh circumference (0.313*), calf circumference (0.271*), shoulder diameter (0.573*), upper arm diameter(0.251*), and BMI (0.271*) coefficient of correlation with ball badminton players performance had been positively with significant level 0.05. Remaining anthropometric measurements not correlated on this present study.

Keywords: Anthropometric, Ball badminton, Measurements, Performance

INTRODUCTION

Ball badminton originated in Tanjore, in Tamil Nadu. It became popular, commanding the interest of the Maharaja of Tanjore. The game attracted many players from southern India, and is about as well-known as cricket in that part of the country. Previously, ball badminton was an attractive game for rural boys since it required a minimum of equipment. The game drew a large number of students from South India, resulting in the formation of the ball badminton federation of India in 1954. Ball badminton eventually spread to Andhra Pradesh, and the first national championship was conducted at Hyderabad in 1956. It was later introduced at the junior and sub-junior levels.

Ball badminton is an indigenous sport of India. It is a racquet game played with a woolen ball upon a court of fixed dimensions by two teams of five player's each. This is also played by two players called Doubles and by only one player

each side called singles. This game was played as early as 1856 by the royal family in Tanjore, capital of Thanjavur district in Tamil Nadu, India. The game is widely prevalent in India and will strike someone new to it as a mixture between volleyball, badminton, and tennis. The game attained popularity in the river basins of Cauvery, Krishna, and Godavari. It is an exceedingly fast game demanding skill, quick perception, correct judgment, and agility of movement and capacity to control the ball with proper movement of wrist.

In ball badminton, anthropometry and motor performance ability of players seem to be the most vital determinants of success. Anthropometric measurements have the potential to quantify the relationship between bone mass, body structure, physical characteristics, and individual players' sporting abilities thereby providing the basis for evaluating sport performance. Anthropometric measurements are often used to classify players according to their respective age or level of performance. Height is an advantage in executing attacking strokes in ball badminton.

Anthropometric profiles of elite athletes provide insight into the requirements for competing at top level in particular

Address for correspondence:

C. S. R. Naveen Kumar

E-mail: naveensportsiit@gmail.com

Table 1: Selected of the anthropometric measurements

Anthropometric measurements	Equipment	Criterion measures
Weight	Weighing machine	Kilograms
Height	Stadiometer	Centimeter
Sitting height	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Hand length	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Upper arm length	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Fore arm length	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Hand breadth	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Upper leg length	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Lower leg length	Anthropometer rod	Centimeter
Foot length	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Foot breath	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Chest circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Upper arm circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Fore arm circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Wrist circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Thigh circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Calf circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Ankle circumference	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Upper arm diameter	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Elbow diameter	Sliding Caliper	Centimeter
Shoulder diameter	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Hip diameter	Flexible tape	Centimeter
Ankle diameter	Sliding Caliper	Centimeter
BMI	Calculation	Percentages

sports. The previous reports have shown that body structure and morphological characteristics are important determinants of performance in many sports and certain physical impressions such as body composition (body fat, body mass, and muscle mass) and physique (somatotype) can significantly influence athletic performance (Carter 1984). Children experiencing early success in a particular sport, not necessarily at a (high) competitive level, might increase their chances for sustained sports participation and an active lifestyle later on. With respect to talent identification, children with a profile that matches the requirements of a specific sport from a young age on will more likely continue training and by consequence have better chances on an optimal talent development pathway. Anthropometric means the scientific study of the measurements and proportion of the human body parts either living or non-living. Anthropometric measurements as an effective role with best performance ball badminton players may to give as best as possible top form. The present study is anthropometric measurements with relation to ball badminton player's performance. Its leads to may won the match.

Table 2: Anthropometric measurements association with ball badminton playing performance

Anthropometric measurements	Coefficient of correlation "r"
Weight	0.364*
Height	0.585*
Sitting height	0.259*
Hand length	0.379*
Upper arm length	0.627*
Fore arm length	0.299*
Palm span	0.239*
Upper leg length	0.462*
Lower leg length	0.389*
Foot length	0.197
Foot breath	0.189
Chest circumference	0.397*
Upper arm circumference	0.201
Fore arm circumference	0.213
Wrist circumference	0.473*
Thigh circumference	0.313*
Calf circumference	0.271*
Ankle circumference	0.179
Upper arm diameter	0.251*
Elbow diameter	0.203
Shoulder diameter	0.573*
Hip diameter	0.117
Ankle diameter	0.113
BMI	0.271*

$n=82$, $r_{.05}(82) = 0.217$, *Significant at 0.05 level

METHODOLOGY

Purpose of the Study

This study would be decided to the anthropometric measurement's relation with ball badminton player's performance.

Selection of the Subjects

The 82 male ball badminton players were selected from national level representation in Andhra Pradesh on non-randomly by purposive sample which is used Table 1.

Collection of the Data and Tools

The data had been collected by administrating the standard procedures for taking anthropometric measurements as well as ball badminton player's performance and tools had been used weighing machine for weight, stadiometer for height and flexible measuring tape for lengths, diameters, and circumference measurements. The score is recorded weights in kgs and remaining the nearest one tenth of the centimeters.

Figure 1: Anthropometric measurements and ball badminton players performance

Statistical Analysis and Discussions

To find out the relationship of anthropometric measurements with ball badminton performance with the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation is used and testing the hypothesis, the level of confidence is 0.05 Table 2.

An analysis of the above table indicates that ball badminton performance is significantly related to measurements height (0.585*), sitting height (0.259*), weight (0.364*), palm span (0.239*), upper arm length (0.462*), forearm length (0.299*), hand length (0.379*), upper leg length (0.627*), lower leg length (0.389*), chest circumference (0.397*), wrist circumference (0.473*), thigh circumference (0.313*), calf circumference (0.271*), shoulder diameter (0.573*), upper arm diameter (0.251*), and BMI (0.271*) as obtained values of correlation were greater than $r = 0.217$ the correlation to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence. The remaining anthropometric measurements as their correlation values are less than $r = 0.217$ need for significance at 0.05 level of confidence Figure 1.

As for the results finally, the study reveals that ball badminton performance ability is significantly related to measurements are height (0.585*), sitting height (0.259*), weight (0.364*), palm span (0.239*), upper arm length (0.462*), forearm length (0.299*), hand length (0.379*), upper leg length (0.627*), lower leg length (0.389*), chest circumference (0.397*), wrist circumference (0.473*), thigh circumference (0.313*), calf circumference (0.271*), shoulder diameter (0.573*), upper arm diameter (0.251*), and BMI (0.271*). As per the analysis,

my suggestion to the coaches, physical directors, physical education teachers, and physical instructors to concentrate on the above anthropometric measurements, while selecting or screening for ball badminton players in a basic level. It may be given effective and top performance in a specific competition.

REFERENCES

1. Borrow HM, McGee R. A Practical Approach to Movements in Physical Education. Philadelphia: Leaand Febiger; 1979.
2. Verma JP. A Text Book on Sports Statistics. Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh: Venus publication; 2000.
3. Nelson NP, Johnson CR. Measurement and Statistics in Physical Education. Belmont, California: Wordsworth Publishing Company Inc.; 1970.
4. Battaglia G, Paoli A, Bellafiore M, Bianco A, Palma A. Influence of a sport-specific training background on vertical jumping and throwing performance in young female basketball and players. *Sports Med Phys Fitness* 2014;54:581-7.
5. Naidu BG, Mohan NV. Criterion anthropometric measurements with relation to fast bowler's performance. *Int J Curr Res* 2017;9:46438-40.
6. Belmont, California, Wordsworth Publishing Company Inc.
7. Naidu BG, Mohan NV. Training performance physical fitness components association with hockey playing. *Int J Multidiscip Educ Res* 2017;6.
8. Naidu BG, Mohan NV. Performance physical fitness components as predictors of Kho-Kho performance ability. *Res J Phys Educ Sci* 2016;4:1-3.
9. Naidu BG, Mohan NV. Criterion performance physical fitness components relation with Kabaddi playing ability. *Res J Phys Educ Sci* 2017;5:1-3.

10. Naidu BG. Relationship of selected performance physical fitness components to the performance of jumpers. *Int J Phys Educ Sports Health* 2016;3:319-22.
11. Naidu BG, Mohan NV. A study of performance physical fitness components of runners, jumpers and throwers. *Int J Phys Educ Sports Health* 2017;4:103-5.
12. Rani TS, Varma RS. Performance physical fitness components relation with badminton players performance ability. *Int J Health Phys Educ Comput Sci Sports* 2017;27:435-6.
13. Naidu BG. Effectiveness of fast bowlers performance relation with specific physical fitness variables. *Asian J Phys Educ Comput Sci Sports* 2018;19:1-3.
14. Available from: <https://www.topendsports.com/sport/badminton/anthropometry.htm>